

Impact Factor: 5.723

ISSN: 2181-0982

DOI: 10.26739/2181-0982

www.tadqiqot.uz

JNNR

JOURNAL OF NEUROLOGY AND
NEUROSURGERY RESEARCH

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 4

2024

ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 5 НОМЕР 4

JOURNAL OF NEUROLOGY AND NEUROSURGERY RESEARCH
VOLUME 5, ISSUE 4

ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

Бухарский государственный медицинский институт и tadqiqot.uz

Главный редактор:

Ходжиева Дилбар Таджиевна
доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Бухарского государственного медицинского
института. (Узбекистан).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5883-9533

Зам. главного редактора:

Хайдарова Дилдора Кадировна
доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентской медицинской академии.
(Узбекистан).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4980-6158

Рецензируемый
научно-практический журнал
“Журнал неврологии
и нейрохирургических исследований”
Публикуется 6 раза в год
№4 (05), 2024
ISSN 2181-0982

Адрес редакции:

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>;
Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Макет и подготовка к печати
проводились в редакции журнала.

Дизайн - оформления:

Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и
информации г. Ташкента Рег. №
от 01.07.2020 г.

“Неврологии и нейрохирургических
исследований” 4/2024

Электронная версия журнала на сайтах:

<https://tadqiqot.uz>
www.bsmi.uz

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Хайдаров Нодиржон Кадирович – доктор медицинских наук, профессор, ректор
Тошкентского государственного стоматологического института. (Узбекистан).

Нуралиев Неккадам Абдуллаевич - доктор медицинских наук, профессор, иммунолог,
микробиолог, проректор по научной работе и инновациям Бухарского государственного
медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Кариев Гайрат Маратович – доктор медицинских наук, профессор, директор
Республиканского научного центра нейрохирургии Узбекистана. (Узбекистан).

Федин Анатолий Иванович - доктор медицинских наук, профессор, заслуженный врач
РФ. Российский национальный исследовательский медицинский университет имени Н.И.
Пирогова. (Россия).

Маджидова Екутхон Набиевна - доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ташкентского
педиатрического медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Рахимбаева Гулнора Саттаровна - доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ташкентской
медицинской академии. (Узбекистан).

Джурабекова Азиза Тахировна – доктор медицинских наук, профессор Самаркандского
государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Мамадалиев Абдурахмон Маматкулович - доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Чутко Леонид Семенович - доктор медицинских наук, профессор, руководитель Центра
поведенческой неврологии Института мозга человека им. Н.П. Бехтеревой. (Россия).

Муратов Фахритдин Хайритдинович - доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентской медицинской академии. (Узбекистан).

Дьяконова Елена Николаевна - доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ивановская
государственная медицинская академия. (Россия).

Труфанов Евгений Александрович – доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Национальной медицинской академии последипломного образования имени П.Л.
Шупика. (Россия)

Норов Абдурахмон Убайдуллаевич – доктор медицинских наук, профессор, главный
врач Бухарского областного многопрофильного медицинского центра. (Узбекистан)

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна – доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Азизова Раъно Баходировна - доктор медицинских наук, доцент Ташкентской
медицинской академии. (Узбекистан).

Давлатов Салим Сулаймонович - Начальник отдела надзора качества образования,
доцент Бухарского государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Саноева Матлюба Жахонкуловна - доктор медицинских наук, доцент Бухарского
государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Артыкова Мавлюда Абдурахмановна - доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Бухарского государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Уринов Мусо Болтаевич - доктор медицинских наук, доцент Бухарского
государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Киличев Ибодулла Абдуллаевич – доктор медицинских наук, профессор Ургенчского
филиала Ташкентской медицинской академии. (Узбекистан).

Нарзуллаев Нуриддин Умарович – доктор медицинских наук, доцент Бухарского
государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Рашидова Нилуфар Сафоевна - доктор медицинских наук, доцент Ташкентской
медицинской академии. (Узбекистан).

Ганиева Манижа Тимуровна - кандидат медицинских наук, доцент Таджикского
государственного медицинского университета (Таджикистан).

Хазраткулов Рустам Бафоевич - доктор медицинских наук, руководитель научного
отдела сосудистой патологии центральной нервной системы Республиканского
специализированного научно – практического медицинского центра нейрохирургии,
профессор кафедры нейрохирургии Центра развития профессиональной квалификации
медицинских работников (Узбекистан).

Нуралиева Хафиза Отаевна - кандидат медицинских наук, доцент Тошкентского
фармацевтического института. (Узбекистан).

Исмаилова Раъно Олимджановна – DSc, руководитель научного отдела патологии
позвоночника и спинного мозга Республиканского специализированного научно –
практического медицинского центра нейрохирургии (Узбекистан).

JOURNAL OF NEUROLOGY AND NEUROSURGICAL RESEARCH

Bukhara State Medical Institute and tadqiqot.uz

Chief Editor:

Khodjueva Dilbar Tadjiyevna

Doctor of medical Sciences, Professor,
Bukhara state medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5883-9533

Deputy editor-in-chief:

Khaydarova Dildora Kadirovna

Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor of the Tashkent
Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4980-6158

Peer-reviewed scientific and
practical journal "Journal of Neurology
and Neurosurgical Research"
Published 6 times a year
#4 (05), 2024
ISSN 2181-0982

Editorial address:

Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>;

Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Layout and preparation for printing
held in the editorial office of the
journal.

Design – pagemaker:

Khurshid Mirzakhmedov

Journal is registered at the Office of
Press and Information Tashkent city,
Reg. No. July 1, 2020

"Neurology and neurosurgical
research" 4/2024

Electronic version of the

Journal on sites:

www.tadqiqot.uz,

www.bsmi.uz

EDITORIAL TEAM:

Khaydarov Nodirjon Kadirovich - Doctor of Medicine, Professor, Rector of Tashkent State Dental Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Nuraliev Nekkadam Abdullaevich - Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Immunologist, Microbiologist, Vice-Rector for Research and Innovation of the Bukhara State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Kariev Gayrat Maratovich - Doctor of Medicine, Professor, Director of the Republican Scientific Center for Neurosurgery of Uzbekistan. (Uzbekistan).

Anatoly Ivanovich Fedin - Doctor of Medical Sciences, professor, Honored Doctor of the Russian Federation. Russian National Research Medical University named after N.I. Pirogova. (Russia).

Madjidova Yokutxon Nabievna - Doctor of Medicine, Professor, Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Rakhimbaeva Gulnora Sattarovna - Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, the Tashkent Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).

Djurabekova Aziza Taxirovna - Doctor of Medicine, Professor, the Samarkand State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Mamadaliyev Abdurakhmon Mamatkulovich - Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor of the Samarkand State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Chutko Leonid Semenovich - Doctor of Medicine, Head of the Center for Behavioral Neurology of the Institute of Human Brain named after N.P. Bekhtereva. (Russia).

Muratov Fakhmitdin Khayritdinovich - Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, the Tashkent Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).

Dyakonova Elena Nikolaevna - Doctor of Medicine, professor of the Ivanovo State Medical Academy. (Russia).

Trufanov Evgeniy Aleksandrovich - Doctor of Medicine, Professor, National Medical Academy of Postgraduate Education named after P.L. Shupika. (Russia).

Norov Abdurakhmon Ubaydullaevich - Doctor of Medicine, professor, Chief Physician of the Bukhara Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center. (Uzbekistan).

Abdullaeva Nargiza Nurmatovna - Doctor of Medicine, professor of the Samarkand State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Azizova Rano Baxodirovna - doctor of medical Sciences, associate Professor of the Tashkent Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).

Davlatov Salim Sulaimonovich - Head of the Department of education quality supervision, associate Professor of the Bukhara state medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Sanoeva Matlyuba Jakhonkulovna - Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of the Bukhara State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Artykova Mavlyuda Abdurakhmanovna - Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor of the Bukhara State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Urinov Muso Boltaevich - Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor, Bukhara State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Kilichev Ibdulla Abdullaevich - Doctor of Medicine, professor of the Urgench branch of the Tashkent Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).

Narzullaev Nuriddin Umarovich - Doctor of Medicine, associate professor of Bukhara State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Rashidova Nilufar Safoevna - doctor of medical Sciences, associate Professor of the Tashkent Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).

Ganieva Manizha Timurovna - Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor, Tajik State Medical University. (Tajikistan).

Hazratkulov Rustam Bafoevich - Doctor of Medicine, head of the scientific department of vascular pathology of the central nervous system of the Republican specialized scientific and practical medical center for neurosurgery, professor of the department of neurosurgery at the Center for the development of professional qualifications of medical workers (Uzbekistan).

Nuralieva Hafiza Otayevna - Candidate of medical Sciences, associate Professor, Tashkent pharmaceutical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Ismailova Rano Olimdjanovna - Doctor of Medicine, head of the spine department of the Republican specialized scientific and practical medical center of neurosurgery (Uzbekistan).

1. Срождинов Сардориддин Шамситдин угли, Солихов Мирилхом Усманович, Нарзиев Нурали Мухамедович, Жумаев Навруз Шухрат угли, Калаш Двиведи, Маматкулова Наргиза Базарбаевна СВЯЗЬ ФИБРИЛЛЯЦИИ ПРЕДСЕРДИЙ И ИШЕМИЧЕСКОГО ИНСУЛЬТА, ГЕНДЕРНЫЕ И ВОЗРАСТНЫЕ РАЗЛИЧИЯ.....	7
2. Adamboev Zufar Ibrahimovich, Samiyev Asliddin Sayitovich, Ergashev Gulom Burievich MODIK TUFAYLI SURUNKALI BEL OG'RIG'I. YECHELMAGAN MUAMMOLAR (ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI).....	13
3. Axmediev Maxmud Mansurovich, Tulayev Nodirbek Bekmurodovich, Arziqulov Jahongir Muzaffarovich BO'YIN-KO'KRAK UMURTQALARIDA JOYLASHGAN ORQA MIYA CHURRASI BÓLGAN BOLALARNING HAYOTI SIFATINI BAHOLASH.....	18
4. Haydarov Nodir Kadirovich, Doniyorova Farangisbonu Alisher qizi EFFECTIVENESS OF PSYCHOMOTOR THERAPY FOR CHILDREN WITH AUTISM: RESEARCH RESULTS.....	23
5. Rakhimbaeva Gulnora Sattarovna, Abdurakhmonova Kutlibika Bakhtiyor kizi COMPARATIVE EFFECTIVENESS OF DUAL ANTIPLATELET THERAPY VERSUS MONOTHERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH ISCHEMIC STROKE.....	26
6. Adamboev Zufar Ibrahimovich, Qilichev Ibadulla Abdullaevich, Nurjonov Abdulla Baxtiyorovich, Samiyev Asliddin Sayitovich COVIDDAN KEYINGI SURUNKALI CHARHASH SINDROMINI DAVOLASHDA “MIYA UCHUN ENERGIYASI” SHIFOBAXSH O‘TLAR ARALASHMASINI SAMARADORLIGI.....	29
7. Мавлянова Зилола Фархадовна, Дониёров Бахриддин Бахром Угли, Джурабекова Азиза Тохировна ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПСИХОЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ У ФУТБОЛИСТОВ В ЗАВИСИМОСТИ ОТ ВОЗРАСТА И ДЛИТЕЛЬНОСТИ ЗАНЯТИЙ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫМ СПОРТОМ.....	33
8. Мирджураев Элбек Миршавкатович, Самиев Аслиддин Саитович, Жиянов Зафаржон Боходирович АНАЛИЗ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПАЦИЕНТОВ С КОГНИТИВНЫМИ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯМИ ПРИ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯХ ХРОНИЧЕСКИХ НАРУШЕНИЯХ МОЗГОВОГО КРОВООБРАЩЕНИЯ.....	36
9. Hidoyatova Dilbar Nabievna, Abdullaeva Muborak Bekkulovna, Khikmatullaeva Shakhnoza Shukurullaevna, Babasheva Dilfuza Ramziddinovna, Dadamukhamedova Mufida Utkirovna, Tursunova Muzayyam Olimovna SIGNIFICANCE OF SECONDARY STROKE PREVENTION AND OPERATIVE TREATMENT ON NEUROLOGICAL AND NEUROPHYSIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TRANSIENT ISCHEMIC ATTACKS.....	39
10. Abdullaeva Muborak Bekkulovna, Nalibaeva Dilorom Umrzakovna, Khamidov Otabek Khayotbekovich, Nurmatov Bobur Makhmudovich, Dadakhanov Ziyovuddin Abdumukhtarovich NEUROLOGICAL ASPECTS OF TMJ DYSFUNCTION WITH DEEP PROSTHETICS.....	44
11. Панжиева Назира Нормухаматовна, Хайдаров Нодир Кадирович, Раимова Малика Мухамеджановна ВЛИЯНИЕ ХИМИОИНДУЦИРОВАННОЙ ПОЛИНЕЙРОПАТИИ НА КАЧЕСТВО ЖИЗНИ И ПОВСЕДНЕВНУЮ АКТИВНОСТЬ У БОЛЬНЫХ С РАКОМ ЯИЧНИКОВ.....	49
12. Сойибов Иброхим Эшмухаматович, Норов Абдурахмон Убайдуллоевич, Хазраткулов Рустам Бафоевич, Тулаев Нодирбек Бекмуродович ПОСЛЕОПЕРАЦИОННАЯ ГИДРОМА ПОСЛЕ ДЕКОМПРЕССИВНЫХ КРАНИОЭКТОМИЙ У ЛИЦ ПОЖИЛОГО И СТАРЧЕСКОГО ВОЗРАСТА.....	53
13. Khaydarova Dildora Kodirovna, Kudratova Shakhodat Ramazonovna STROKE AND CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE: EPIDEMIOLOGY, PATHOGENESIS, AND MANAGEMENT ACROSS KIDNEY DISEASE STAGES.....	56
14. Касымова Сайёра Акмалджановна, Каюмова Нафиса Камилджановна, Абдувалиева Гавхар Тулкуновна КЛИНИЧЕСКИЙ СЛУЧАЙ ПОЗДНЕГО ПРОЯВЛЕНИЯ БОЛЕЗНИ ШАРКО-МАРИ- ТУТА (СЛУЧАЙ ИЗ ПРАКТИКИ).....	59
15. Бердиева Хилолахон Умаржановна, Садыкова Гулчехра Кабуловна ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ УРОВНЯ РЕЧЕВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ У ДЕТЕЙ ПРИ НЕВРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПАТОЛОГИЯХ.....	61

16. Madjidova Yakutkhon Nabieva, Asimova Nodira Mirvasidovna, Rakhmonov Islombek Abdurashid ugli COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF NEURASTHENIC DISORDERS IN MEN WITH INFERTILITY.....	66
17. Abdullaeva Muborak Bekkulovna, Dadakhanov Ziyovuddin Abdumukhtarovich, Nurmatzoda Otabek Akhmadjonovich, Khamidov Otabek Khayotbekovich, Akhmedova Yulduz Gayratovna NEW ASPECTS OF IDENTIFICATION OF NEUROVASCULAR CONFLICTS.....	69
18. Умирова Сурайё Мамуржонова, Усмонов Бахром Муродович ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ НАНОТРОПИЛА В ЛЕЧЕНИИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ ВЕРТЕБРОБАЗИЛЯРНОЙ НЕДОСТАТОЧНОСТИ.....	75
19. Xodjimatom Umidjon Jasurbekovich, Azizova Ra`no Baxodirovna APPLICATION OF SCREENING TOOLS FOR ASSESSMENT OF COGNITIVE IMPAIRMENTS IN PATIENTS WITH STATUS EPILEPTICUS.....	79
20. Хасанов Хабибулло Абдухоликович, Казухито Такеучи, Якубов Жахонгир Баходирович, Алиходжаева Гульнарохон Алаутдиновна СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОЙ ТАКТИКИ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ МЕНИНГЕАЛЬНЫХ СОЛИТАРНЫХ ФИБРОЗНЫХ ОПУХОЛЕЙ ФАЛЬКСА.....	84
21. Эшқувватов Гайрат Эркинович, Асадуллаев Улугбек Максудович, Якубов Жахонгир Боходирович, Хожиметов Дилшод Наимович ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЕ ИНТРАОПЕРАЦИОННОЙ КРОВОПОТЕРИ И РОЛЬ ПРЕДОПЕРАЦИОННОЙ ЭМБОЛИЗАЦИИ В ЛЕЧЕНИИ ГИПЕРВАСКУЛЯРИЗИРОВАННЫХ МЕНИНГИОМ ГОЛОВНОГО МОЗГА.....	90

UDC:616.697

Madjidova Yakutkhon Nabievna
Asimova Nodira Mirvasidovna
Rakhmonov Islombek Abdurashid ugli
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute
Andijan State Medical Institute

COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF NEURASTHENIC DISORDERS IN MEN WITH INFERTILITY

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13834792>

ANNOTATION

This article presents the result of a study of the manifestations of neurasthenia, which is significantly predominant in men with infertility, while the most common complaints of a neurosthenic nature were irritability, general weakness and sleep disorders.

Keywords: men, infertility, neurasthenia, somatoform disorders.

Маджидова Якутхон Набиевна
Азимова Нодира Мирваситовна
Рахмонов Ислонбек Абдурашид угли
Тошкент педиатрия тиббиёт институти
Андижон давлат тиббиёт институти

БЕПУШТЛИК БИЛАН ОҒРИГАН ЭРКАКЛАРДА НЕВРАСТЕНИК КАСАЛЛИКЛАРНИНГ ҚИЁСИЙ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақолада бепуштлиқ билан оғриган эркакларда сезиларли даражада устун бўлган неврастениянинг намоён бўлишини ўрганиш натижалари келтирилган, неврастеник табиатнинг энг кўп учрайдиган шикоятлари асабийлашиш, умумий заифлик ва уйқу бузилиши эди.

Калит сўзлар: эркаклар, бепуштлиқ, неврастения, соматоформ касалликлари.

Маджидова Якутхон Набиевна
Азимова Нодира Мирваситовна
Рахмонов Ислонбек Абдурашид угли
Ташкентский педиатрический медицинский институт
Андижанский государственный медицинский институт

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА НЕВРАСТЕНИЧЕСКИХ НАРУШЕНИЙ У МУЖЧИН С БЕСПЛОДИЕМ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье представлены результаты исследования проявлений неврастения, значительно преобладающей у мужчин с бесплодием, при этом самыми распространенными жалобами неврастенического характера были раздражительность, общая слабость и нарушение сна.

Ключевые слова: мужчины, бесплодие, неврастения, соматоформные расстройства.

Relevance: The difficulty of determining the exact etiology of the development of male reproductive sterility in a given patient underlies long-term diagnostic measures, the duration of which can reach several years, aggravating chronic stress and neurological abnormalities in males with reproductive sterility.[1,2]. The male body is more sensitive to stress due to the peculiarities of sexual reactivity and resistance, and chronic stress can lead to sexual dysfunctions and deterioration of the spermogram. Scientific works in this area using modern diagnostic methods and neurological therapy techniques are of great importance, but at the same time the lack of evidence on the etiopathogenetic role of neurological abnormalities that caused the development of sterility in men is not noted in the literature. Psychological stress is also perceived

as a potential clinical risk factor that can reduce male fertility. Studies examining the relationship between male infertility and psychological stress have yielded conflicting results.[3,4].

Purpose of the study: to study neurasthenic manifestations in men with infertility.

Materials and methods of research: To achieve the goals and objectives of the study, 80 men aged 20 to 33 years were examined from partner couples who had been in an infertile marriage for more than 2 years; the control group consisted of 30 practically healthy men.

We divided these men into 2 groups according to the nature of their infertile marriage: the 1st group (main) consisted of 50 men with various fertility disorders, and the 2nd group (comparison) consisted of 30 men

with normal reproductive function, in whom the cause of their infertile marriage was the female factor. In addition, a control group was examined, which consisted of 30 practically healthy men who were married and had children.

In addition, in order to study in detail and compare the results of the examination of the specifics of somatic and neurotic reactions of men depending on the duration of infertility, we divided the patients based on the recommendation of J. Mert (1998) [13]. Three groups were defined: group A - men in an infertile marriage from 1 to 2 years, group B - men in an infertile marriage from 3 to 5 years and group C - men in an infertile marriage for more than 6 years.

Research results:Complaints presented by men in infertile marriages can be combined according to ICD-10 into the section of neurological spectrum disorders associated with severe stress and

somatoform disorders [F40-F48]. We then conducted a detailed analysis of all subjective symptoms of the men we examined and combined them into certain symptom complexes in accordance with the ICD subheadings of the above disorder. Thus, we can identify 2 main symptom complexes in men in infertile marriages: somatoform disorders (F45.0) and neurasthenia (F48.0).

As we see from Figure 1, neurasthenia is the predominant syndrome and occurs on average in 72% of men in the main and 56.7% of the comparison group, the difference between them was insignificant. Somatoform disorders, in turn, were less common, but as we see, they occurred almost 2 times less often ($p = 0.024$) in patients of the comparison group (30%) than in the main group (56%), while among them there were hypochondriacal disorders, somatoform dysfunction of the autonomic nervous system, as well as somatoform pain syndromes.

Figure 1. Average number of patients with the main symptom complexes of neurotic disorders.

Based on the data obtained during the analysis, neurasthenia was more common in the main group (72%) than in the comparison group, and the differences found were statistically significant ($p = 0.048$; Pearson Chi-square). In turn, when analyzing somatoform disorders, we were unable to identify statistically significant differences ($p = 0.166$; method: Pearson Chi-square). In addition, 10% of the examined men in the control group had neurasthenia, while only 3.3% of men in this group had somatoform disorders.

It should also be noted that patients most often had a combined nature of disorders, in which it was impossible to note the predominance of one or another syndrome complex. When comparing the clinical syndrome depending on the group, statistically significant differences were revealed ($p = 0.049$; method: Pearson Chi-square). The relationship between the group of men and the clinical syndrome was average (Cramer's $V = 0.31$). In the main group, we see the predominance of a combination of syndromes (46%), while in the comparison group, either a characteristic neurasthenic syndrome (45.5%) or somatoform disorders (31.8%) were most often formed.

Based on the obtained data, when comparing sleep disorders, anxiety, irritability, general weakness and sexual dysfunction depending on the group, statistically significant differences were revealed ($p = 0.013$, $p = 0.040$, $p < 0.001$, $p < 0.001$, $p = 0.005$ respectively; Pearson Chi-square), while the difference in other signs was insignificant.

As we see from the results of the study, neurasthenia significantly prevailed in men with infertility, and the most common complaints of a neurasthenic nature were irritability, general weakness and sleep disturbance. These complaints were significantly more often observed in the main group (90%, 82% and 62%, respectively), while in the comparison group these figures were 50%, 36.7% and 33.3%, respectively ($p = 0.013$, $p = 0.040$, $p < 0.001$, respectively). The feeling of tension was more often encountered in men in marriages with a female factor of infertility (43.3%), while in infertile men this figure was 30%, however, there was no statistical difference between the groups ($p = 0.226$).

The incidence of complaints such as fatigue during daily activities, cognitive impairment, headaches and dizziness in both cases in both groups was approximately the same and we were unable to identify statistically significant differences.

The decrease in cognitive functions was more often complained about in the group of men with impaired fertility, while there was no difference in the control and comparison groups and this indicator was almost equal. It should be noted that these complaints in the subjects were not relieved by rest. In persons with neurasthenia, high susceptibility to loud sounds, noise, and bright light was also noted; these manifestations were noted by the majority of the subjects.

In the majority of individuals with neurasthenia, GBN is detected in 36.3% of cases, which in turn proceeded with sensations of a constricting hoop in 24.1% of cases and as a feeling of a heavy head in 75.9% of cases.

Sexual disorders are one of the leading manifestations in the clinic of neurasthenia, in males these disorders were manifested by the presence of early ejaculation and decreased erectile function, as well as a decrease in sexual activity. Among our patients, sexual disorders significantly prevailed in the group with male infertility (52% of men), however, 20% of men in an infertile marriage due to the female factor also complained of periodic sexual disorders ($p = 0.008$ *).

The course of neurasthenia in our patients can be divided into 2 types: hyposthenic and hypersthenic. The first type was characterized by fatigue, decreased performance, and drowsiness in the first half of the day; this category of patients was dominated by signs of depressive disorders, and especially in patients of the main group who had been in an infertile marriage for more than 6 years, neurasthenia took on a chronic character, which was manifested by asthenodepressive syndrome. The second type, hypersthenic, was most often prevalent in men in the comparison group; they were most often characterized by irascibility, excitability, and sleep disorders in the form of difficulty falling asleep, while this category of patients was dominated by anxiety disorders with signs of impaired autonomic reactivity. It should be noted

that patients in the comparison group who had been in an infertile marriage for more than 6 years had a characteristic "irritable weakness", which includes signs of both hypersthenic and hyposthenic types of neurasthenia.

As for sleep disorders, in men in infertile marriages, they were mainly manifested by inadequate and superficial sleep with a large

number of vivid dreams, as well as difficulties in falling asleep. Patients complained of a lack of vigor after waking up, while the general state of health improved at lunchtime, with a repeated deterioration in the afternoon.

We examined the quality of life of males from childless married couples in comparison with a control group.

Assessment of the quality of life in childless married couples of the study groups

Indicator	Warp	Comparison	Control	
General health	74.4 ± 2.6	78.8 ± 2.4	85.7 ± 3.3	<0.001*123
Physical functioning	90.1 ± 2.5	91.9 ± 1.8	93.0 ± 2.1	<0.01*12
Role physical functioning	84.1 ± 4.2	88.2 ± 5.3	89.9 ± 6.0	<0.01*12
Role emotional functioning	81.9 ± 7.6	86.0 ± 5.5	90.1 ± 5.5	<0.001*2 <0.05*13
Social functioning	76.5 ± 4.2	84.0 ± 5.5	87.3 ± 5.5	<0.001*12 0.0333
Viability	66.9 ± 3.5	71.5 ± 2.4	78.6 ± 2.8	<0.001*123
Mental health	68.5 ± 4.5	73.9 ± 4.7	84.0 ± 4.8	<0.001*123

* - Differences between groups; 1 - Differences between groups under 3 and 4-6 years; 2 - Differences between groups under 3 and 7-10 years; 3 - Differences between groups 4-6 years and 7-10 years

According to the presented table, when assessing the general health status, physical functionality, role and emotional and social functioning, as well as mental health depending on the group, significant differences were found ($p < 0.001$; Fisher's F-test). The quality of life of patients in the main group in all areas was significantly lower than that of patients in the comparison group and the control group, while in men in an infertile marriage associated with the female factor in the area of physical and role functioning, there were no differences with the control group.

Men in the main group rated their general health at 74.4 ± 2.6 points, while in the comparison group it was 78.8 ± 2.4 , and in the control group it was 85.7 ± 3.3 points. In terms of physical functioning, men in infertile marriages demonstrated high scores, with this score being 90.1 ± 2.5 for infertile men and 91.9 ± 1.8 for men with infertile spouses, which did not differ from the score in the control group. However, the differences in the area of role physical functioning between the main group and the comparison group increased and amounted to 84.1 ± 4.2 and 88.2 ± 5.3 points, while the difference between the comparison and control groups (89.9 ± 6.0) remained virtually at the same level. More pronounced differences are seen in the area of role emotional functioning, social functioning and mental health, and overall vitality. Men in infertile marriages assess emotional functioning (which assesses the impact of the psycho-emotional state on the performance of daily work, thus worsening its quality, increasing the time spent on it, and influencing emotional life) at 81.9 ± 7.6 and 86.0 ± 5.5 points for the main group and the comparison group, respectively, while those in men with children – at 92.1 ± 5.5 points. The lowest rated areas are mental

health and vitality, for example, in the area of mental health, men in infertile marriages rate it as 68.5 ± 4.5 points for men in the main group and 73.9 ± 4.7 points for men in the comparison group, and the area of vitality is even lower – 66.9 ± 3.5 points for the main group and 71.5 ± 2.4 points for the comparison group.

Social functioning, which assesses the impact on interaction with others and the degree of limitation of social activity in both groups of men in an infertile marriage also differed greatly: 76.5 ± 4.2 points in men in the main group and 84.0 ± 5.5 points in men in the comparison group, which was close in value to the control group (87.3 ± 5.5 points). It is interesting to note that pain intensity differed only in the main group (81.8 ± 2.9 points), possibly due to somatophoric pain disorders, but the differences with the comparison and control groups were not high (86.6 ± 2.4 and 87.6 ± 2.5 points, respectively), which may indicate that the presence or absence of children does not greatly affect this aspect of quality of life.

Conclusions: Thus, the prevalence of neurasthenic disorders is significantly lower in men in an infertile marriage with a female factor of infertility than in men with impaired fertility. If in the main group, disorders of a mostly depressive nature with the addition of comorbid disorders prevailed, then in the men of the comparison group, insecurity, increased suspiciousness and anxiety were noted in the character traits. When assessing the parameters of quality of life in men in an infertile marriage, it is necessary to take into account the duration of the infertile marriage, and at this stage of the study, we noted various features of the assessment of the quality of life of men in an infertile marriage, more pronounced in the main group.

Literature:

1. Motuzova S.V. Lpersonality-oriented approaches in diagnostics and complex therapy of neurotic disorders.//Journal of Psychiatry and Medical Psychology. 2017.No. 3 (39). P. 71-72.
2. Stepanova N.V., Blagoveshchenskaya I.V.Structural and dynamic features of personality organization of patients with neurotic disorder Bulletin of the Samara Humanitarian Academy. Series: Psychology. 2018.No. 2 (24). P. 47-61.
3. Changes in ego strength in patients with neurotic and personality disorders treated with a short-term comprehensive psychodynamic psychotherapy./Cyranka K, Rutkowski K, Mielimąka M, et al.//Psychiatr Pol. 2018 Feb 28;52(1):115-127. doi: 10.12740/PP/OnlineFirst/40020. Epub 2018 Feb 28.PMID: 29704419
4. Effectiveness of intensive group psychotherapy in the treatment of neurotic and personality disorders./Mielimąka M, Rutkowski K, Cyranka K, et al.//Psychiatr Pol. 2015 Jan-Feb;49(1):29-48. doi: 10.12740/PP/26093.PMID: 25844408

ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 4

JOURNAL OF NEUROLOGY AND NEUROSURGERY RESEARCH

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 4

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Тадqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000